

Review Article

UV–Vis operando spectroelectrochemistry for (photo)electrocatalysis: Principles and guidelines

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Abstract

Electrocatalytic and photoelectrocatalytic technologies are key players in the transition to a circular economy. In order to rationally design the new generation of efficient (photo)electrocatalysts it is critical to establish which performance bottlenecks must be overcome during the complex catalytic transformations. Obtaining such detailed mechanistic and kinetic knowledge requires the use of *operando* spectroscopic techniques that are capable of probing the system under operating conditions. Of all the methods available UV–Vis spectroelectrochemistry stands out for its versatility and experimental simplicity which enables the systematic study of samples under a wide range of reaction conditions. From a mechanistic viewpoint, this technique allows us to quantify the accumulation of reactive species at the catalyst–electrolyte interface and, through a kinetic population model, opens the door to characterising the kinetics of the rate determining step of catalysis. Here, we review the different information that can be extracted from UV–Vis spectroelectrochemistry and how it can be used to understand catalytic mechanisms in solid (photo)electrodes.

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(Photo)electrocatalysis, Solar-driven chemical transformations, UV-Vis spectroelectrochemistry, Reaction mechanisms.

Introduction and background

(Photo)electrocatalytic ((P)EC) reactions driven by renewable energies are a powerful tool to decarbonise our industries and enable a circular economy [1]. Today, it is possible to produce green chemicals, fuels and fertilisers using sunlight energy, water, CO₂ and/or N₂ [2]. However, despite great strides in the last decades, the efficiency and stability of the current conversion processes are still low when using Earth abundant materials. The underlying problem are parasitic reactions that deactivate the catalysts or slow chemical steps that limit the overall activity [3]. Addressing these efficiency bottlenecks is paramount to enable (photo)electrocatalysis at large scales.

In this direction, the characterisation of (P)EC systems under operational conditions is essential to gain knowledge about the catalytic cycle (Figure 1a) and degradation pathways. In particular, it is essential to identify: **(i)** the structure and chemical nature of the active sites and key reaction intermediates, especially those accumulated during the steady-state of the catalysis. This includes: oxidation states, geometric/electronic structure and coordination environment [4,5]. **(ii)** The different reaction pathways and their corresponding kinetics, with special attention to those of the rate determining step of the catalysis [6,7]. **(iii)** Possible changes at the (photo)electrocatalyst–electrolyte interface, that is, reactive surface, leading to the formation of defects and the reconstruction or degradation of the surface [8–12]. Note here that we define the reactive surface of the electrode as the top atomic layers in contact with the electrolyte which are primarily responsible for the catalytic activity.

Characterisation of electronic and structural properties

Traditionally, most of the structural and chemical (**i** and **iii**) characterisation of (photo)electrodes (including bulk, nanostructured, and supported molecular solid materials) has been carried out *ex-situ* due to experimental challenges. In recent years, techniques commonly used to study materials *ex-situ* have been explored and adapted to study (photo)electrocatalytic processes and catalyst's changes in *operando* conditions. Recent advances have enabled bypassing the limitations

Figure 1

UV-Vis Spectroelectrochemistry (SEC) to study (photo)electrocatalysts in action. (a) Schematic representation of a catalytic cycle to produce green chemicals. The catalyst can transition through pre-catalytic, catalytic and fast transition states. The slowest step in the cycle is the rate-determining-step (RDS) which leads the accumulation of active species (A). The kinetics of the RDS can be studied as a function of temperature (T), the kinetic isotopic effect (KIE) and pH. (b) Flow diagram of key parameters to consider when using SEC to extract kinetic information. (c) Schematic representation of a SEC set-up exemplifying the capabilities of the technique. Note that analogous cell configuration can be used in time-resolved experiments which complement SEC by providing information about intermediate and structural dynamics [25,40–43].

related to the structural and crystalline characteristics of the studied materials in addition to the presence of a liquid electrode–electrolyte interface. These include: X-ray-based spectroscopies, such as XAS, XES and XPS, Mössbauer, IR, Raman- and surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopies in addition to microscopies such as STEM and STM [13–22]. All of them enable the study of the structure and chemical nature of the catalysts. However, many of these techniques require expensive equipment preventing wider and regular use. Importantly, these restrictions often hinder the rapid screening of multiple samples under different reaction conditions, a process of critical importance at the first stages of catalyst development and optimisation.

To overcome these limitations UV–Vis spectroscopy coupled with electrochemical measurements (UV–Vis spectroelectrochemistry) offers the prospect of a powerful yet inexpensive and easy-to-use tool to perform a first/initial catalyst characterisation. Critically, UV-Vis spectroelectrochemistry provides two main advantages for catalyst screening, in comparison to other methods such as those based on X-ray spectroscopy techniques: (1) its experimental simplicity and the use of wavelengths from the UV–Vis to the near-IR in the 300–2000 nm range, allows studies to be carried out in multiple reaction configuration, matching

more closely those of catalytic operation, testing, for example, different (photo)electrochemical cell set-ups and reaction conditions (temperatures, pH, aqueous or organic electrolytes, etc.). (2) The method allows facile characterisation of the catalyst response at multiple timescales ranging from femtoseconds to seconds under the same experimental conditions [23]. Despite these advantages, it is important to consider the limitations of UV–Vis spectroscopy. While the method can probe specific electronic transitions such as ligand to metal charge transfer (LMCT) in complexes and metal oxides, and thus provide electronic and even structural information [24–26], this technique lacks the breadth of chemical and structural sensitivity offered by other methods. For example, UV–Vis, spectroscopy cannot easily distinguish the exact chemical environment or even the oxidation state of an active catalytic species. Moreover, we note that UV–Vis spectroscopy, (1) when used in transmission mode is not, in principle, surface sensitive, (2) when used in reflective mode, its surface sensitivity will depend on the penetration depth of the probe light and (3) monolayer surface sensitivity is practically inaccessible. Consequently, UV–Vis spectroscopy is not designed to replace in-depth structural and chemical characterisation methods, but to complement them. Indeed, despite the advent of new characterisation methodologies, UV–Vis spectroscopy

(and electrochemistry) remains the workhorse of (photo)electrocatalysts design.

Characterisation of reaction kinetics

Beyond the characterisation of the electronic structure, the elucidation of specific mechanistic information, such as the reaction kinetics or the nature of different reaction pathways (point-ii), has traditionally been achieved solely by electrochemical means. In particular, electrocatalytic activity has generally been studied using Tafel analyses, measuring the electrode current–potential (J - V) response, where J equals the reaction rate (for Faradaic processes) and V has usually been correlated with the reaction driving force. The interpretation of such J - V curves can be difficult and extracting information about the rate determining step (RDS) of the reaction and its kinetics often requires complex theories. For example, when the RDS of a given reaction is limited by an electron transfer elementary reaction, the Tafel slope (upon plotting $\text{Log } J$ vs. V) is usually interpreted using the Butler–Volmer equation to conclude on the mechanism and its kinetics [27]. However, such analysis is usually complex for non-ideal catalysts and is hampered by the dynamical nature of the, bias-dependent, electrocatalytic interface, including surface reconstruction/degradation as well as local pH, intermediates binding energies and capacitance changes [28,29]. Additionally, this type of analysis often involves the assumption of a constant potential-dependent coverage of intermediate species, ignoring possible changes in the population of accumulated species at the RDS and their effect on the overall kinetics [23]. For the widely studied hydrogen evolution reaction, Tafel slopes have been calculated to vary between 30, 40–120 mV dec^{-1} depending on the nature of rate limiting step of the reaction (Tafel, Heyrovsky and Volmer, respectively) [27]. However, for NiMo alloys Tafel slopes between 121 and 148 mV dec^{-1} have been reported, these values could be explained by two different mechanisms depending on the surface coverage of adsorbed H atoms (Volmer and Heyrovsky with high surface coverage) [30]. Such surface coverage dependent behaviour in addition to the lack of standardised experimental methodologies to determine Tafel slopes can lead to misleading interpretation of these electrochemical microkinetic analyses [31].

In this line, recent publications [7,32,33] have shown that these traditional electrochemical methods often provide only a partial picture of (photo)electrode reactivity highlighting the need to couple electrochemical analyses with *operando* techniques to understand the complex nature and chemical changes occurring at polarised interfaces during catalysis. This includes capturing changes in the surface structure due to

reconstructions as well as monitoring changes in the population of reactive intermediates. Although UV–Vis spectroscopy by itself cannot provide details in the morphology, crystallinity, oxidation state or chemical nature of adsorbed species on the (photo)electrocatalyst surface, it has the potential to distinguish changes in these properties. Thus, of the different *operando* methods, UV–Vis spectroscopy is one of the most versatile and inexpensive which allows monitoring the concentration of accumulated species and the screening of a wide range of (photo)electrocatalysts under multiple reaction conditions, such as different pH, temperatures, substrates and isotopic labelling. Here we revisit the combination between UV–Vis spectroscopy and electrochemical experiments and discuss the experimental factors that must be considered to study catalytic mechanisms on (photo)electrocatalysts in *operando* conditions (Figure 1b).

UV–Vis spectroelectrochemistry: Combining the optical and electrochemical response

UV–Vis spectroscopy is a widely used technique to study the optical properties and reaction kinetics of catalysts, especially homogenous and molecular heterogeneous catalysts [34]. When coupled to electrochemical experiments the method is known as UV–Vis spectroelectrochemistry (SEC) [35–38]. In such combined experiments, the oxidation states and concentration changes of the catalysts can be monitored by probing their absorption fingerprint and quantified through the well-known Lambert-beer law (Equation (1))

$$A = \epsilon \cdot l \cdot c \quad (1)$$

where A is the absorbance, ϵ is the extinction coefficient ($\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$), l is the medium path length (cm), c the molar concentration (M). Crucially, in UV–Vis SEC, the absorbance is measured while simultaneously monitoring the current flowing through the circuit (Figure 1c) enabling a correlation of the current and optical responses as a function of (i) the applied potential and (ii) different electrolyte environments and reaction conditions (Figure 1c). While UV–Vis SEC has been extensively used to study molecular systems, it can also be applied to (photo)electrodes. To study a specific reaction (oxidation or reduction) this is often done in a 3-electrode cell configuration (our focus here) [39].

In the following sections we review recent developments in the analysis and interpretation of UV–Vis SEC to draw kinetic and mechanistic information in (photo)electrodes. We focus on examples of promising metal oxides for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) such as IrOx and NiOOH. As evidenced by numerous recent studies,

during electrochemical reactions metal oxides undergo chemical and structural changes which manifest in modulations of their electronic and atomic structure directly impacting electronic transitions ($d-d$ or ligand–metal charge transfer) which can be readily monitored by UV–Vis spectroscopy. Here, we discuss: **(1)** the monitoring and quantification of accumulated and reactive species at the electrochemical interface at different applied potentials; **(2)** the distinction between bulk and surface processes; and **(3)** the elucidation of kinetic and mechanistic parameters including pH sensitivity, the kinetic isotope effect or the activation energy of a given reaction (Figure 1c) [44–52].

(1) Monitoring and quantifying the accumulation of different species at the interface

In electrocatalytic systems, changes in the chemical nature of the electrode can be induced when varying the applied potential. In systems that exhibit a high tendency to localise charges, this can effectively result in the generation and accumulation of reactive species and in changes in their oxidation state. UV–Vis spectroelectrochemistry provides a powerful tool to characterise

those changes if the modulations impact optical transitions in the UV–Vis. In particular, the accumulation of different redox species can be tracked by spectrally resolving the change in the optical signal as a function of the applied potential. Such spectral evolution is observed in the case of IrOx electrodes [53] and an Ir dimeric molecular catalyst $[\text{Ir}_2(\text{pyalc})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\mu\text{-O})]^{2+}$ [54], where three different redox species could be distinguished due to their distinctive optical fingerprints (Figure 2a). Analysis of the bias-dependent optical signals revealed the change of these redox species that transitioned from OER pre-catalytic Ir^{3+} -containing states to OER catalytically active oxidised Ir^{4+} -containing states with increasing bias (Figure 2b). In this particular example, the spectral assignment was enabled by comparison of IrOx with the optical response of a molecular dimer containing Ir^{3+} - Ir^{3+} being oxidised to Ir^{4+} - Ir^{5+} reported by Crabtree and co-workers, and by complementing UV–Vis with crystallography, XPS and DFT calculations [35]. The ability to simultaneously monitor the increasing density of Ir^{4+} -containing states with the current density in both the molecular Ir and IrOx electrocatalysts, allowed to correlate the cooperative effect of multi-metallic sites with the evolution of oxygen (Figure 2c) [53].

Figure 2

Spectrally-resolved changes in the oxidation states of IrOx. (a) Absorption changes of IrOx upon applying an oxidative potential in 0.1 M HClO_4 aqueous solution at pH 1.2. (b) Changes in the concentration of redox states as a function of the applied potential and their correlation with the OER current. Data extracted from the study by Bozal-Ginesta et al. [53] (c) Schematic representation of the cooperative effect of multi-metallic Ir sites to evolve oxygen.

(2) Bulk vs surface redox processes

While SEC is not directly a surface selective technique, different strategies can be applied to establish if the observed species are localised at the surface or in the bulk of the material. One of the most straightforward methods is to perform studies as a function of sample thickness. This is exemplified in Figure 3 for the case of NiOx electrodes [55] that undergo different transformations during activation and catalysis. The bulk nature of the first redox process ($\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2 \rightarrow \text{NiOOH}$) was evidenced by a strong thickness dependence of both the JV response (Figure 3a) and the optical response of the electrode at potentials before the OER catalysis onset (Figure 3b). On the other hand, the optical response associated with the second redox process ($\text{NiOOH} \rightarrow \text{NiOOH}(+)$) was observed to be independent of the film thickness (Figure 3c), and correlated with the current, suggesting a surface preference. Consequently, $\text{NiOOH}(+)$ was assigned to be accumulated at the reactive surface (Figure 3c) as shown schematically in Figure 3d.

(3) Kinetic and mechanistic information

When the RDS is chemical in nature, the population of accumulated species during the steady-state of the

catalysis will determine the overall kinetics of reaction. Under such conditions, SEC data can provide key kinetic parameters. For example, in the catalytic cycle shown in Figure 1a, the transformation of A into the final products can be described as follows:

$$v = \frac{-d[A]}{dt} = J = k_{\text{rds}} \cdot [A]^\alpha \quad (3)$$

where, k_{rds} is the kinetic constant of the RDS of the catalytic cycle, α is the reaction order of the accumulated species A to overcome the RDS and the reaction rate (v) equals the measured current density (J , $\text{e}^- \text{s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$). Thus, a classic rate law analysis can be derived from Equation (3) as

$$\log J = \log k_{\text{rds}} + \alpha \cdot \log[A] \quad (4)$$

Using spectroelectrochemical measurements, changes in the concentration ($[A]$) can be monitored through its optical absorbance (upon determining its extinction coefficient) whilst the current (rate of the reaction) is simultaneously recorded. Such data can be plotted using Equation (4) in order to determine the order of the reaction that drives the RDS as well as the kinetic constant (k_{rds}) of the same process (i.e. when $[A] = 1$).

Figure 3

Surface versus Bulk processes in NiOx catalysts. Three different NiOx samples with thicknesses 5 nm (green), 10 nm (red), 20 nm (blue) were studied. (a) 50th CV scan at 50 mV s⁻¹ in 0.1 M KOH electrolyte. (b) Spectroelectrochemistry showing the change in absorbance after activation for each sample with respect to the absorbance before activation. This change is associated with the initial redox wave observed in (a). (c) Spectroelectrochemistry data applying 0.1 V beyond the catalytic onset to ensure each sample is examined under the same catalytic regime. Data extracted from the study by Corby *et al.* [55] (d) Graphic representation of each thickness of NiOx sample showing the relative thicknesses of the active material (NiOOH(+), grey) to bulk oxidised NiOOH (yellow) and unaltered NiOx (orange). Only the upper 5 nm or less are active for water oxidation.

This approach has been used to study NiOOH and FeOOH (see Figure 4 for FeOOH example) as electrocatalysts for OER at pH 14 [56]. Under such conditions, it was found that the reaction order α , transitions from 1 to 4 upon increasing the applied potential up to 0.43 V overpotential. This indicates that upon a high surface coverage, 4 accumulated species need to interact (Figure 4b), possibly undergoing equilibria, to overcome the RDS of the catalysis (Figure 4c). It is key to emphasise that in the studied potential range the monitored species are equal in chemical/redox nature (subsection 1), as indicated by their almost identical UV–Vis spectra (inset Figure 4a) [34]. To correctly apply equation (4) the accumulated species must be equivalent in nature throughout the studied potential range, because different chemical/redox species can exhibit different reactivity and undergo different catalytic mechanisms with different kinetics.

While the analysis described above is performed under steady-state conditions, an alternative strategy to probe the kinetics in electrocatalysts is to monitor the optical transient decays of such accumulated species after steady-state of catalysis (Figure 4d). The optical change at the very first moments can be approximated to the

studied catalytic reaction, considering a Faradaic efficiency of unity. Consequently, these time-resolved data points can be fitted to the differential rate law ($v = -\frac{d[A]}{dt}$ in Equation (3)) to obtain equivalent conclusions to such obtained using the rate law equation (Figure 4e). As indicated in Figure 4f for the FeOOH example the kinetic data extracted from these two different methods are very similar, validating both analyses. The selection of the appropriate timescale for such decay analyses will depend on the turnover frequency of the reaction, that is, the timescale of the RDS, which for the case of the OER lies within millisecond to second timescale.

Experimental considerations

Recent experimental advances in UV–Vis spectroelectrochemistry and data interpretation have opened the door to access key kinetic and mechanistic information on solid (photo)electrochemical systems presenting optical changes in the visible region [6,23,48,51,56]. Such data need to be carefully and critically analysed since different and complicated processes can take place. The following key questions should be answered during this analysis: **(1)** Are different species observed? **(2)** Is the spectral response the same in the studied potential range? **(3)** Are the observed species located in the bulk or

Figure 4

Rate law analysis of OER in FeOOH. (a) Increasing the applied potential changes the nature and concentration of the accumulated species. FeOOH(+) refers to the species accumulated before the catalysis and FeOOH(++) the species accumulated after the onset of the catalysis. Inset: Normalised spectra for FeOOH(++). (b) Rate law for the observed catalytic species. (c) Schematic mechanistic proposal according to the order 4 observed in the rate law. (d) Simultaneous measurement of the 500 nm optical signal (blue trace), expressed as concentration, and electrode potential (black trace) induced by the application of a 0.44 V overpotential to FeOOH, and then switching to open circuit. (e) Optical decay fitting when the catalytic overpotential (-0.44 V overpotential) has been turned off. (f) Table summarising the estimated k_{rds} from the rate law or through the decay fitting. Data extracted from the study by Francàs et al. [56].

at the surface of the catalyst? (4) Is there only one catalytic process taking place (Faradaic efficiency of unity)? Provided that only a single surface species can be observed and it can be associated with the target catalytic process, then one can proceed to extract kinetic and mechanistic parameters from the data, as depicted in the flow diagram in Figure 1c. However, we emphasise that to obtain a chemical relevant picture of the accumulated species UV–Vis SEC needs to be complemented with other chemical sensitive *operando* spectroscopic techniques such as XPS, XAS, RAMAN, IR as well as DFT calculations that inform about the chemical nature of the different accumulated species.

Outlook

The power of UV–Vis spectroelectrochemistry resides in its versatility. Beyond the limited examples provided above, UV–Vis SEC can be further exploited to gain more mechanistic information when performing this analysis under different experimental conditions such as: (1) different pH values (in the case of water) to gain knowledge on the role of OH[−] in the RDS; (2) using deuterated solvents yielding the kinetic isotopic effect (KIE), which is indicative of the involvement of a H bond breaking during the RDS; and (3) different temperatures to obtain activation energies [57]. Such approach has recently been applied to the study of water, methanol and ethanol oxidation on hematite photoanodes but systematic studies are still scarce [6,52,58].

These type of analysis can be the cornerstone to understand and rationalise (photo)electrocatalysts efficiency and can be further implemented to evaluate which are the best electrocatalysts to be incorporated into a photoelectrode, since the electrocatalyst's intrinsic kinetics will be important to yield an efficient system [59]. In this direction future mechanistic studies in electrocatalytic systems should consider a set of different techniques allowing us to depict not only the chemical nature of the accumulated species, but also the reaction kinetics and other key parameters such as KIE, activation energy, order of the reaction, etc. Such information would allow us to draw plausible reaction mechanisms and help enable the future generation of more efficient catalysts.

Declaration of competing interest

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- ** of outstanding interest

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